

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY
8 St. Andrew's Place, London, NW1 4LB

OI-486 1527

President: PROFESSOR CHARLES THOMAS, M.A., F.S.A.

Hon. Secretary: MR. P. J. FOWLER, M.A., F.S.A.

Secretary: MISS B. DE CARDI, F.S.A.

1st January, 1973

Dear Andrew

Qatar Survey

A brief note to let you know that I have just heard that my proposals (enclosed) have been approved in principle and that I shall be going out to discuss the detailed arrangements with the Qatar Government, probably early in March.

I shall need to be fully briefed as to your requirements in the light of these proposals so that I can make the necessary inquiries when I am in Dohar. For instance, it would be helpful to have a brief note indicating how you would carry out your part of the survey; number of workmen required if you will be digging; stationery and photographic requirements; special equipment and other needs. We shall have to keep equipment sent out from the U.K. to a minimum and if I went armed with a full list I could find out what is likely to be available locally.

It would probably be useful if members of the team could meet to discuss plans over a glass of sherry. Would you be free on Friday, 9th February, to attend a meeting here at 5.30 p.m.? Perhaps you would let me know as soon as possible; your shopping list, etc. can follow later.

All good wishes,

Yours sincerely,

A. G. Williamson, Esq., M.A.,
West End, Wootton,
Woodstock, Oxon.

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WRITE NOW E

POB 73

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CONGRATULATIONS

DEANITELY

PALM TRENE ANDRE